

JUVENILE DELINQUENCY ARRIVE GENERAL DESCRIPTION

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Annotation: *This article covers the general description, causes and enabling conditions of juvenile delinquency.*

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There are different views on explaining the causes of delinquency, including the causes of juvenile delinquency. Many explain this with various conflicts in society (economics, politics, social relations, ideology and other areas). Unfortunately, the criminological literature does not have a clear understanding of what should be understood as the causes of crime and its factors. In some cases, these two concepts are confused or overlapped. These cases also apply to the problem of the causes and conditions of juvenile delinquency [1].

Thus, this approach to explaining the causes of crime is related to socio-psychological factors that cause crime, primarily motives (subjective reasons). Conditions are considered as macro and micro environment. In this, the main attention is paid to the microenvironment, because it is at this level that the individual is socialized[2].

It can be said that the second approach to explaining the reasons for the commission of crimes and the conditions that made them possible is also worthy of attention for other reasons.

Some scientists include the following among the causes of juvenile delinquency: negative influence of living, studying or working environment; that teenagers who drop out of school do not engage in certain work for a long time; conditional factors that

determine the improper upbringing of a teenager; testimony of older criminals; the influence of books and films depicting violence and lawlessness[3].

When talking about two different approaches to explaining the causes of crime, one more difference should be noted.

A second approach to explaining the causes of crime is related to interaction. The cause itself manifests itself through the interaction with the conditions and produces the effect.

It affects the formation of deficits in social psychology at the microenvironmental level, and directly affects specific individuals through social institutions at the microenvironmental level. The subjective cause, that is, the interaction between the individual's state of inclination and the situation in which the individual is (objective conditions) occurs only on a single level. It is this interaction that produces the effect[4].

On the other hand, the interaction (in this case, the interaction between the specific situation and the dispositional state of the individual) cannot be realized through its final result, the consequence (crime). Likewise, an effect cannot affect its cause (a person's dispositional state) which has already occurred and disappeared after the effect has occurred[5].

We can divide the causes and factors of juvenile delinquency into the following groups:

- factors in the economic and social sphere - changes in economic processes (increase in prices, inflation, increase in poverty, etc.), increase in the level of unemployment, divorces in society, addiction of teenagers to drugs and alcohol products, failure of the social protection system, etc.;

- social-psychological factors - the existence of injustices in society, the impact of divorce on the psyche of a minor, the weakness of spiritual and educational propaganda and the strengthening of elements of mass culture, the low level of legal culture, as well as the negative impact of media and modern social networks in the form of video, audio, and photos various unethical information;

- factors (deficiencies) in the administrative-organizational sphere - slowness of authorities in working with minors, solving their problems, deficiencies in the activity of entities involved in the prevention of juvenile delinquencies, low level of cooperation, in particular, deficiencies in identifying and keeping records of this type of delinquency. It should be said that the issue of responsibility of the minor offender who committed the offense is not resolved or he is not notified (concealed) of the fact that he has committed an offense to the appropriate body, it creates a feeling of disdain for the moral rules and legal norms in the mind of the minor, and this causes even more problems. will be.

Analyzing juvenile delinquency and its prevention is the main link in the fight against crime in the society as a whole. According to data, 50-60% of recidivists start their "criminal career" as a minor, still a teenager. Therefore, determining how early juvenile delinquency and their steps on the antisocial path, preventing them, guarantees that the state's criminal-legal policy will be effective in the future. Before addressing the issue of juvenile delinquency, who is a juvenile? it is necessary to pay attention to such issues as what are their specific characteristics, their legal status in international and national legislation.

The criminological features of juvenile and youth crimes can be explained as follows. Adolescence is the period when a person's personality is formed. At this stage, a person is extremely changeable, that is, very susceptible to negative environmental influences. Due to insufficiently developed sense of self-control in adolescents, "social stagnation" resulting from such events, social adaptation defects are relatively easy to manifest in the form of antisocial acts, and sometimes they are strengthened as stable behavior, which becomes more difficult to return to the right path over time. The most important thing is that from this period they should start forming their personality and make a choice to determine the future path. Of course, during this period, teenagers, family, and society need help.

In certain periods, classical, positive and other schools of criminology looked at crime as a theological, psychological, biological, social phenomenon. Also, the relationship between personality and crime depends on the age factor.

They consider that not only subjective factors, but also external influences play an important role in how early a person commits a crime. The influence of external, objective influences on the personality and psychology of adolescents should always be under certain control, the role of family, neighborhood and society is important in this place.

It is also important to know what characteristics juvenile delinquency, especially criminality, is acquiring today. Criminologists have found a stable relationship between those who are on different medical lists (alcoholism, drug addiction, mental illness, etc.) based on the percentage of the total number of juvenile prisoners.

Also, there is a close relationship between juvenile delinquency and family and family relations, we can see that this indicator is low in areas where families are in a conflict environment, where there are many divorces, and where there are many divorces, this indicator is low.

It is known that such crimes include crimes committed by individuals between the ages of 14 and 18. Due to the fact that the achievement of social, psychological and physiological maturity leads to the emergence of a number of legal consequences, it is absolutely important to strictly separate minors from adults. Having such a strict limit is of great importance in the implementation of justice.

Juvenile delinquency has a number of specific characteristics, which are first of all manifested in the causal complex and motivation of the formation of criminal behavior, as well as in its level and development trends. At the same time, the listed characteristics are also related to the personal qualities of minors and their social and legal status in society. Therefore, juveniles differ from adults in many personal characteristics and criminal behavior.

Most of these international documents have been ratified by the Republic of Uzbekistan and their main principles and rules have been used in the formation of our national legislation.

In the effective organization of the protection of the interests of minors, legal education and legal problems of family strengthening are of particular importance. Because a strong family is one of the most important foundations of a civil-legal society, and it is a social environment where minors grow as individuals. It is urgent to direct the activities of all relevant specialists in this direction - pedagogues, doctors, sociologists, lawyers, etc. to this goal. Juvenile delinquency is one of the main issues in the subject of criminology, and the development of a definition that reflects its content in detail is of great scientific-theoretical and practical importance. In the social sense, crime is a behavior capable of endangering the rights and interests of society, citizens and public associations, which makes it difficult for the development of social relations and causes their disruption.

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